

1 **THE ROLE OF CYTOKINE LICENSING IN SHAPING THE THERAPEUTIC**
2 **POTENTIAL OF WHARTON'S JELLY MSCs: METABOLIC SHIFT TOWARDS**
3 **IMMUNOMODULATION AT THE EXPENSE OF DIFFERENTIATION**

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24 **Abstract**

25 *Background*

26 Cytokine licensing with pro-inflammatory molecules, such as tumour necrosis factor-alpha
27 (TNF- α) and interferon-gamma (IFN- γ), has emerged as a promising strategy to enhance the
28 therapeutic potential of multipotent mesenchymal stromal cells (MSCs). While licensing has
29 demonstrated benefits for immunomodulation, its effects on other key MSC functions,
30 including differentiation and paracrine activity, remain incompletely explored.

31 In this study, we evaluated the transcriptomic, metabolomic, and functional changes induced
32 by short-term TNF- α /IFN- γ priming of Wharton's jelly-derived MSCs (WJ-MSCs).

33 *Methods*

34 WJ-MSCs were expanded and exposed to TNF- α and IFN- γ (10 ng/ml each) for 24 hours.
35 Transcriptomic analysis was performed using RNA sequencing to identify differentially
36 expressed genes related to immune modulation and lineage commitment. Metabolomic
37 profiling was conducted using high-resolution mass spectrometry to assess changes in
38 metabolic pathways. Functional assays evaluated the effects of cytokine priming on induced
39 differentiation and growth factor secretion.

40 *Results*

41 Cytokine licensing induced notable alterations in gene expression, upregulating pathways
42 linked to immune response, inflammation, and cytokine signalling. However, short-term
43 cytokine treatment significantly attenuated the osteogenic and adipogenic differentiation of
44 MSCs, as evidenced by the reduced expression of RUNX2, ALP, CEBPA, and PPARG. The
45 priming had a negligible effect on EGF, FGF-2, HGF, LIF, and SCF secretion. The production
46 of VEGF-A and VEGF-C was elevated, although the levels remained low. Metabolomic
47 analysis revealed enhanced kynurenine pathway activity, indicative of increased tryptophan
48 catabolism, accompanied by elevated levels of fatty acids and polyamines.

49 *Conclusions*

1
2 50 Our findings demonstrate that TNF- α /IFN- γ priming reprograms WJ-MSCs by enhancing their
3 51 immunomodulatory capacity at the expense of differentiation potential. These results highlight
4 52 the need for tailored strategies to optimize MSC functionality for specific clinical applications.
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9 54 **Keywords:** multipotent mesenchymal stromal cells, Wharton's jelly, cytokine priming,
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11 55 transcriptomics, metabolomics, adipogenic and osteogenic differentiation, secretome.
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57 **Background**

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59 Regenerative medicine is an advancing field offering substantial promise for
60 addressing diseases that lack effective conventional treatments. Among cell-based
61 approaches, multipotent mesenchymal stromal cell (MSC)-based has gained significant
62 prominence. These cells, known for their ability to differentiate into osteoblasts, chondrocytes,
63 and adipocytes, are highly valued for their potent paracrine signalling and immunomodulatory
64 properties (1, 2). Through the release of cytokines, growth factors, and extracellular vesicles,
65 MSCs mediate their effect on key regenerative processes, including angiogenesis, immune
66 modulation, and extracellular matrix remodelling (2, 3).

67 Wharton’s jelly-derived MSCs (WJ-MSCs), isolated from the gelatinous connective
68 tissue of the umbilical cord, have emerged as a particularly promising cell type due to their
69 easy accessibility through non-invasive methods. Compared to MSCs from adult tissues, WJ-
70 MSCs exhibit a more primitive phenotype, higher proliferative potential, and enhanced
71 plasticity, making them strong candidates for regenerative applications. (1, 4). They exhibit
72 robust paracrine activity, secreting various trophic factors that facilitate tissue repair and
73 immune modulation. Moreover, these cells are less affected by donor age and environmental
74 influences, making them more consistent for clinical use. Compared to highly potent
75 embryonic stem cells, WJ-MSCs present no ethical concerns, enhancing their appeal for
76 therapeutic use.

77 Despite the mentioned advantages, WJ-MSC-based therapy faces notable challenges.
78 Donor-to-donor variability significantly affects key therapeutic properties, including
79 proliferation rate, differentiation capacity, and immunomodulatory activity (2, 5, 6), posing
80 barriers to successful clinical translation.

81 In addition to intrinsic factors, the lack of reproducibility and high failure rates observed
82 in advanced-stage MSC-based clinical trials are caused by extrinsic factors happening upon
83 transplantation (2). After injection, cells encounter hostile microenvironments characterized by

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2 84 inflammation, hypoxia, and altered extracellular matrix composition, which compromise cell
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4 85 viability, functionality, and integration. Resulting moderate clinical efficacy underscores the
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6 86 need for novel strategies to optimize MSC functionality and resilience.

7 87 Preconditioning strategies, such as hypoxic culture, three-dimensional culture
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9 88 systems, and cytokine licensing, have emerged as promising methods to enhance MSC
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11 89 properties by mimicking physiological or inflammatory cues encountered *in vivo* (3, 7, 8).
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13 90 Cytokine licensing, in particular, has shown considerable promise in augmenting the
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15 91 therapeutic properties of MSCs. This approach involves exposing MSCs to pro-inflammatory
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17 92 cytokines, such as tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) and interferon-gamma (IFN- γ), which
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19 93 primes the cells to synthesise higher levels of immune-regulatory molecules, e.g., indoleamine
20
21 94 2,3-dioxygenase (IDO), interleukin-6 (IL-6), prostaglandin E2 (PGE2), programmed death-
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23 95 ligand 1 (PD-L1) and human leukocyte antigen-G (HLA-G) (9, 10). Recent studies have shown
24
25 96 that cytokine licensing does not introduce additional donor-donor variability (11). Moreover,
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27 97 the upregulation of immunomodulatory genes following cytokine licensing was remarkably
28
29 98 synchronized despite initial donor-to-donor cell variability (12). Harmonization of the
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31 99 transcriptomic profile was shown even on the single-cell level within the single-donor
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33 100 heterogenic MSC populations (13). Considering the allogeneic nature of the WJ-MSC-based
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35 101 therapies, the achievement of synchronized cell phenotype may increase the reproducibility
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37 102 of treatment results.

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42 103 Although cytokine licensing has demonstrated its utility in unifying immunomodulatory
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44 104 functions, its impact on other MSC attributes, such as differentiation capacity, metabolic
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46 105 activity, and secretion of growth factors, remains insufficiently characterized. Addressing these
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48 106 knowledge gaps is crucial to determine whether cytokine licensing can serve as a universal
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50 107 enhancement strategy or whether its efficacy is limited to specific applications.

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53 108 In this study, we provide new insights into the effects of cytokine licensing on WJ-
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55 109 MSCs, mainly focusing on their adipogenic and osteogenic differentiation potential, paracrine
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57 110 activity, and metabolic changes. Combining transcriptomics, metabolomics, and functional
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59 111 assays, we aim to provide a multi-dimensional understanding of how short-term exposure to

112 TNF- α and IFN- γ influences WJ-MSC behaviour, revealing both beneficial and detrimental
1 effects.

114

115 **Methods**

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117 ***Cell isolation, culture and licensing***

118 Discarded human umbilical cords were obtained from healthy full-term neonates
14 (N = 7) after spontaneous delivery. About 10 cm of the umbilical cord was aseptically collected,
16 119 placed in sterile PBS with antibiotic–antimycotic solution at 4 °C, and transported to the
18 120 laboratory within 24 hours. After washing several times in PBS and brief exposure to 10%
20 121 Betadine (EGIS Pharmaceuticals PLC, Budapest, Hungary), blood vessels were removed,
22 122 and the remaining Wharton’s jelly tissue was chopped into small fragments (1–2 mm³).
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27 124 WJ-MSCs were isolated from fragments (1 g) by enzymatic digestion in PBS-AA
28 125 solution containing 0.26 U/ml Liberase™ TM (Roche Custom Biotech, Mannheim, Germany)
29 126 and 1 mg/ml hyaluronidase at 37°C with constant shaking for 2 hours. After removing of
31 127 undigested fragments with 40- μ m cell strainers, cells were centrifuged at 450 \times g for
33 128 10 minutes. Obtained pellet was diluted in a complete culture medium containing α -MEM
35 129 (Gibco®, Thermo Fisher Scientific), 5% pooled PL (Bioinova, Ltd.), penicillin/streptomycin
37 130 (Gibco®, Thermo Fisher Scientific), and GlutaMAX (Gibco®, Thermo Fisher Scientific), and
39 131 cultured at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere, with 5% CO₂. Regular media changes were
41 132 done twice a week. After reaching near-confluence, cells were harvested using the 0.05%
43 133 Trypsin/EDTA solution (Gibco®, Thermo Fisher Scientific) and reseeded onto a fresh plastic
45 134 surface (Nunc, Roskilde, Denmark) at a density of 5 \times 10³ cells/cm². Cells at passages 3-5
47 135 were used for subsequent experiments (1, 14).

54 136 For the cytokine licensing, cells were cultured during 24 hours in α -MEM,
55 137 supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS, Gibco®, Thermo Fisher Scientific),
57 138 penicillin/streptomycin, GlutaMAX, and 10 ng/ml each of TNF- α and IFN- γ (15).

139 **RNA extraction and sequencing**

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2 140 Total RNA was extracted using the QIAGEN RNeasy Mini Kit, followed by ribosomal
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4 141 RNA depletion with the QIAGEN RiboMinus Eukaryote System (N = 7). RNA libraries were
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6 142 prepared with the QIAGEN QIAseq Stranded Total RNA Library Kit, which included the steps
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8 143 of RNA fragmentation, cDNA synthesis, end repair, adapter ligation, and PCR amplification.
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10 144 Sequencing was performed on an Illumina platform, generating 150 bp paired-end reads.
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12 145 Quality control and pre-processing involved FastQC and Trimmomatic (16, 17). Reads were
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14 146 aligned to the human reference genome (GRCh38) using a STAR aligner, and transcript
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16 147 quantification was done with feature Counts (18). Differential expression analysis was
17
18 148 performed using DESeq2 (19), and genes with an adjusted p -value < 0.05 and \log_2 fold change
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20 149 > 1 were considered significant.
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24 150 **Gene Set Enrichment Analysis**

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26 151 Data were analysed in [GeneCore facility \(Institute of Biotechnology of the CAS\)](#) with R
27
28 152 programming language v4.2.2 (20). Rlog transformed data were used in PCA and
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30 153 heatmap.org.Hs.eg.db v3.15.0 (21) database was used for ENSEMBL ID–gene symbol
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32 154 conversion. Differential gene expression was assessed using DESeq2 v1.36 package (19).
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34 155 DEGs were identified using the following parameters: baseMean > 100 , padj < 0.05 , $|\log_2FC|$
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36 156 > 1 . Gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) was carried out using the GSEA software v4.3.3
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38 157 (22, 23), [assessed in August 2024](#). The gene list was ranked based on p -adjusted values.
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40 158 [Data were compared to Human collections of Molecular Signatures Database](#), particularly
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42 159 [Hallmark gene sets](#), [WikiPathways gene sets](#), [KEGG Medicus gene sets](#), [Reactome gene](#)
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44 160 [sets](#), and [gene ontology \(GO\) biological process gene sets](#). Calculated FDR q and NES values
45
46 161 [were used to build the graph presented in Figure 1B](#). Significant terms were considered those
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48 162 [with FDR \$q\$ values \$< 0.25\$ \(\$-\log_{10}\$ FDR \$q > 0.602\$ \) \(22, 23\)](#).
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53 163 **Metabolomics**

54
55 164 The metabolomic and lipidomic profiles of cells was explored by the liquid
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57 165 chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS) in the Metabolomics core facility at the Institute
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59 166 of Physiology of the CAS. For lipidomics and metabolomics, cells were grown on 6-well plates,
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167 treated as required, quickly washed with PBS, snap-frozen, and stored at -80 °C. Metabolites
168 were extracted using a biphasic solvent system of cold methanol, methyl tert-butyl ether, and
169 water (24).

170 An aliquot of the bottom (polar) phase was collected and cleaned using an
171 acetonitrile/isopropanol mixture. After evaporation, the dry extract was resuspended in 5%
172 methanol with 0.2% formic acid, followed by separation in an Acquity UPLC HSS T3 column
173 (Waters). Another aliquot of the bottom phase was evaporated, resuspended in an
174 acetonitrile/water mixture, and separated in an Acquity UPLC BEH Amide column. Metabolites
175 were detected in negative and positive electrospray ion mode (Thermo Q Exactive Plus
176 instrumentation) (25). Signal intensities were normalized to the respective total ion count (TIC)
177 before subsequent statistical analysis.

178 **Seahorse assay**

179 Parallel measurement of mitochondrial respiration and glycolytic rate was performed
180 using Seahorse XF24 Analyzer (Agilent Technologies, USA) and a modified Seahorse XF Cell
181 Mito Stress Test. Two days before the experiment, 10⁴ cells (N=6) were plated in triplicates in
182 poly-L-lysine-coated assay plate wells and cultured overnight under standard culture
183 conditions. The cell monolayers were treated with a mixture containing 10 ng/ml of TNF- α and
184 10 ng/ml of IFN- γ for 24 hours. One hour prior to the experiment, the cells were washed with
185 1 ml of XF Assay Medium, i.e., 1 \times DMEM lacking bicarbonate, HEPES, and glucose, and
186 containing 2 mM glutamine, 1 mM pyruvate, and 1% FBS, pH 7.4, 37 °C. Afterward, the
187 microplate was incubated at 37 °C. 16-24 hours prior experiment, the XFe24 Sensor Cartridge
188 was prepared by incubation with XF Calibrant at 37 °C. Basal metabolic rate without any
189 oxidative substrate and rates after the subsequent addition of the following substrates and
190 inhibitors were recorded: glucose (10 mM), oligomycin (Oligo, 2.5 μ M), FCCP (FCCP, 4 μ M),
191 and a mixture of rotenone (Rot, 1 μ M), antimycin A (AA, 0.5 μ M), and 2-deoxyglucose (2DG,
192 100 mM). For precise normalization of rates according to cell counts, immediately after
193 Seahorse measurements, cell nuclei were stained with Hoechst 33342 (final concentration
194 1 μ l / ml). Images of each well were acquired by Cytation 3 Cell Imaging Reader (BioTek) and

195 analysed using software Gen5 (BioTek) to obtain cell counts for each well. Nuclei counts were
196 used to normalize OCR and ECAR rates (per 10⁴ cells).

197 ***Early osteogenic and adipogenic differentiation***

198 The WJ-MSCs (N=4, in duplicates) were seeded into 6-well plates (10⁵ cells per well),
199 allowed to adhere overnight, and then treated by TNF- α and IFN- γ as described previously.
200 After 24 hours of cytokine treatment, the culture medium was changed to complete medium
201 without inducers or differentiation media for adipogenic or osteogenic induction.

202 To induce osteogenic differentiation, the cells were cultured for 7 days in a medium
203 composed of α -MEM supplemented with 10% FBS (Gibco®, Thermo Fisher Scientific),
204 penicillin/streptomycin, GlutaMAX, 10 mM glycerol-2-phosphate, 0.1 μ M dexamethasone and
205 100 μ M L-ascorbic acid (all from Merck). The medium was changed every 2 days. *After 7 days*
206 *of culture, cells were collected for the qPCR analysis. In parallel, the alkaline phosphatase*
207 *expression was assessed using the Fast Blue RR Salts/Naphthol kit (Merck), according to the*
208 *manufacturer's instructions, and evaluated by light microscopy.*

209 For adipogenic differentiation, WJ-MSCs were cultured for 7 days in a medium
210 composed of α -MEM, containing 10% FBS, penicillin/streptomycin, GlutaMAX, 0.5 mM 3-
211 isobutyl-1-methylxanthine, 0.1 μ M dexamethasone, 0.1 mM indomethacin, and 10 μ g/ml
212 insulin (all from Merck). The medium was replaced every 2 days. *After 7 days of culture, cells*
213 *were collected for the qPCR analysis. In parallel, the accumulation of intracellular lipid droplets*
214 *was evaluated by Nile Red (1 μ g/ml in PBS, Merck) staining, according to the manufacturer's*
215 *instructions. The cells were assessed using a fluorescent microscope (Leica, Germany). A*
216 *quantitative analysis of the Nile Red fluorescence intensity in investigated groups was done*
217 *in a microplate reader (Tecan Infinite 200; Tecan, Switzerland) at 550 nm / 640 nm*
218 *wavelengths using a multiple point reading mode (100 reading points per well). The data were*
219 *presented as an average Nile Red fluorescence intensity for each condition after the*
220 *subtraction of negative control values (obtained from noninduced cells) and normalized by the*
221 *number of cells detected by DAPI staining.*

222 After 7 days of culture, WJ-MSCs were harvested by trypsinization and centrifuged.

223 The pellets were washed once with PBS and stored at -80°C for subsequent qPCR analysis.

224 **Quantitative real-time PCR**

225 To assess the efficacy of differentiation, specific human marker genes were selected:

226 • Osteogenic markers: RUNX2 (Runt-related transcription factor 2,

227 Hs.PT.56a.19568141), COL1A1 (Collagen type I alpha 1 chain, Hs.PT.58.15517795),

228 ALPL (Alkaline phosphatase, liver/bone/kidney, Hs.PT.56a.40555206) and OCN

229 (Osteocalcin, Hs.PT.56a.39318706.g);

230 • Adipogenic markers: CEBPA (CCAAT/enhancer-binding protein alpha,

231 Hs.PT.58.4022335.g) and PPARG (Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor

232 gamma, Hs.PT.58.25464465).

233 Total RNA was extracted from cell pellets using the Total RNA Purification Kit (Norgen

234 Biotek Cor., Canada), following the manufacturer's protocol. The concentration and purity of

235 RNA were assessed using a NanoDrop™ 2000/2000c Spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher

236 Scientific). The RNase-Free DNase I Kit (Norgen Biotek Corp., Canada) was used for RNA

237 purity improvement. RNA samples with an absorbance ratio (A260/A280) between 1.9 and 2.1

238 were used for subsequent experiments.

239 For the quantitative conversion of RNA into single-stranded cDNA, we applied a High-

240 Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The reaction mix

241 contained 1 μL 10x RT Buffer, 0.4 μL 25x dNTP Mix, 1 μL 10x RT Random Primers, 0.5 μL

242 MultiScribe™ Reverse Transcriptase, 0.5 μL RNase Inhibitor, 1.6 μL Nuclease-free water

243 and finally diluted RNA was added. RNA samples were normalized to the same amount of

244 input RNA for reverse transcription. Reverse transcription was performed using the C1000

245 Touch™ Thermal Cycler (Bio-Rad, USA) set to these conditions: 25°C for 10 min, 37°C for

246 120 min, 85°C for 5 min and 4°C for the end.

247 The reaction mixtures were prepared using 5 μL TATTA SYBR® GrandMaster® Mix

248 (TATTA Biocenter AB, Sweden), 2.6 μL RNase free water, 0.4 μL Primers (forward and

249 reverse primer, IDT), lastly 2 μL the cDNA was added. Quantitative real-time PCR was carried

250 out using the CFX384 Touch Real-Time PCR Detection System (Bio-Rad, USA) following
 251 these cycling conditions: initial denaturation at 95 °C for 3 s, followed by 44 cycles of
 252 denaturation at 95 °C for 5 s, and annealing at 60 °C for 30 s extension for 72°C for 10 s.

253 The following primer pairs (PrimeTime® qPCR Primers, IDT) were used in the study:

Genes	Forward primers (5'-3')	Reverse primers (5'-3')
RUNX2	CTTCACAAATCCTCCCAAGT	AGGCGGTCAGAGAACAAAC
COL1A1	GACATGTTTCAGCTTTGTGGAC	TTCTGTACGCAGGTGATTGG
ALPL	CGAGAGTGAACCATGCCA	TCCCTGATGTTATGCATGAGC
OCN	CTCACACTCCTCGCCCTAT	CGCCTGGGTCTCTTCACT
CEBPA	CCACGCCTGTCCTTAGAAAG	CCCTCCACCTTCATGTAGAAC
PPARG	GTTTCAGAAATGCCTTGCAAGT	GGATTCAGCTGGTTCGATATCAC
PPIA	GTGGCGGATTTGATCATTGG	CAAGACTGAGATGCACAAGTG

254
 255 All samples were in technical triplicates, and no-template controls (NTCs) were
 256 included to monitor potential contamination. Amplification efficiency and melt curve analysis
 257 were performed using CFX Maestro Software (Bio-Rad). Relative gene expression levels were
 258 calculated using the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method, comparing induced samples to non-induced (control)
 259 samples. PPIA (Peptidylprolyl Isomerase A, Hs.PT.58v.38887593.g) was used as the
 260 reference gene for normalization.

261 ***Secretome composition***

262 The growth factor concentration was assessed in the conditioned medium of primed
 263 and unprimed WJ-MSCs (N=4). Briefly, MSCs at passage 3 were seeded at the density 10^5
 264 cells per well of a 6-well plate and cultured overnight. Then, the cytokines (TNF- α and IFN- γ
 265 at 10 ng/ml) were added to the culture medium. and the MSCs were cultured for an additional
 266 24 hours. The conditioned medium was collected and centrifuged at 1,500 rpm for 10 min and
 267 immediately stored at -80 °C. Concentrations of EGF, FGF-2, HGF, LIF, SCF, VEGF-A,
 268 VEGF-C, IL-8, CXCL10, CCL5, MCP1, IL-6, and sVCAM-1 were assessed by Luminex®-

269 based multiplex ProcartaPlex® Immunoassay (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.), according to the
270 manufacturer's instructions. The measurement was performed on a Bio-Plex 200 Instrument
271 (Bio-Rad, Prague, Czech Republic). All samples were analysed in duplicates. The cytokine
272 and growth factor concentrations (pg/ml) were derived from the measured Mean fluorescence
273 intensity (MFI) using fitted standard curves (14).

274 **Statistical analysis**

275 *RNA Sequencing*

276 Differential expression analysis was performed using DESeq2, and genes with an adjusted p-
277 value < 0.05 and log2 fold change > 1 were considered significant.

278 *Metabolomics*

279 For volcano plots, p-values were calculated using Welch's test in RStudio, version 1.4,
280 using the matrixTests package <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=matrixTests>. Multivariate
281 analysis was performed in MetaboAnalyst 5.0 (26). Statistically significant p-values are
282 indicated in the figures as follows: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001, and ****p < 0.0001.

283 *Seahorse analysis*

284 After normalization according to cell count, a paired t-test was performed. The same
285 donors were used for both the control and experimental groups. Statistically significant p-
286 values are presented in figures as follows: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001.

287 *Luminex-based immunoassay and PCR data analysis*

288 A paired t-test was carried out to compare the levels of growth factors/cytokines or
289 gene expression in primed and unprimed cells. The same donors were used for the control
290 and experimental groups, ensuring a within-subjects analysis. Data analysis and visualization
291 were performed using Prism 10.2.3. Statistically significant p-values are presented in figures
292 as follows: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001, ****p < 0.0001.

293

294 **Results**

295 ***Effect of cytokine licensing on the transcriptomic profile of WJ-MSCs***

296 To explore the effect of TNF- α and IFN- γ treatment on WJ-MSCs, we performed RNA
1 sequencing and analysed differentially expressed genes.
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4 298 The principal component analysis (PCA) demonstrated a robust transcriptional
5 distinction between untreated WJ-MSCs and their cytokine-primed counterparts (Fig.1A).
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7 299 Independent of the initial donor-donor variability of gene expression patterns in the untreated
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9 300 cells, the cytokine licensing resulted in substantial transcriptional reprogramming of WJ-MSCs
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11 301 and unification of their phenotype.
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15 303 The cytokine licensing resulted in a significant (log₂ fold change >1 or <-1; p<0.001)
16 change in the expression of 665 genes (Additional file 1). According to the Gene Set
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18 304 Enrichment Analysis (GSEA) (Fig. 1B), the most upregulated pathways driven by the priming
19
20 305 corresponded to the immune response, inflammation, and cytokine signalling indicating an
21
22 306 enhanced immune activation in the treated cells (Fig. 1B). These findings were consistent
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24 307 across multiple pathway databases, including KEGG, Reactome, and GO:BP. Notably, the
25
26 308 enrichment score (ES) for the Interferon Gamma Response and TNF- α signalling via NFKB
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28 309 pathways confirmed that the genes associated with these pathways were predominantly
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30 310 upregulated and highly ranked (Fig 1.C). In addition, the mild activation of the apoptosis
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32 311 pathway was detected, indicating a normal stress response to inflammatory stimuli.
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36 313 While immune-related pathways were the most prominently altered, our analysis
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38 314 revealed statistically non-significant trends or borderline significance changes across multiple
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40 315 metabolic pathways. Slight but consistent upregulation of fatty acid metabolism, unfolded
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42 316 protein response, shifts in expression pattern for oxidative phosphorylate, and glycolysis-
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44 317 related genes were detected.
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48 319 Given the known interplay between metabolic reprogramming and MSC functionality,
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50 320 these trends warranted further investigation into their potential biological relevance.
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53 322 Next, we examined transcriptional changes in differentiation pathways to assess
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55 323 whether cytokine licensing impacts the lineage commitment of WJ-MSCs (Fig. 2) [using gene
56 ontology \(GO\) terms related to the theoretical differentiation potential of MSC. Within each
57 pathway, we identified genes using a threshold of p<0.05, regardless of the fold-change value.](#)
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2 325 This threshold was chosen to capture a broader spectrum of genes within each selected
3 pathway. The identified genes (Additional file 2, table 1) were then manually categorized
4 326 based on fold change ranges (>1, 0.5–1, <0.5, <-0.5, -0.5 to -1, and >-1), and the number of
5 genes in each category was used for data visualization. Analysis of gene ontology (GO) terms
6 327 revealed the almost equal distribution of up- and down-regulated genes within the parent cell
7 differentiation pathway (GO:0030154). A similar tendency was observed in child GO terms,
8 328 which reflects explicitly the differentiation capacity of the MSCs. Proportionate distribution of
9 up- and downregulated genes was observed for chondrocyte (GO:0002062), osteoblast
10 (GO:0001649), smooth muscle (GO:0051145) and neuron (GO:0030182) differentiation. In
11 329 the case of the fat cell differentiation pathway (GO:0045444), despite the overall gene
12 distribution being almost the same, more genes were allocated in the strongly downregulated
13 330 cluster. The largest share of downregulated genes appeared in the myoblast differentiation
14 pathway (GO:0045445).
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21 Together, these results confirm the robust transcriptional reprogramming induced in
22 MSCs by the short-term cytokine licensing. However, despite the strong activation of pathways
23 responsible for immunomodulatory activity, no clear evidence of the positive or negative action
24 339 of the priming towards the other functional properties of MSCs (i.e., differentiation-related) was
25 340 detected.
26 341

27 342 ***Effect of cytokine licensing on the adipogenic and osteogenic differentiation***

28 Even subtle transcriptomic shifts in metabolic pathways or differentiation markers may
29 343 reflect biologically meaningful trends that underpin the functional adaptation of MSCs to
30 344 cytokine exposure.
31 345

32 To reveal the effect of short-term cytokine licensing on the osteogenic and adipogenic
33 346 differentiation, the primed and unprimed MSCs were cultured under lineage-specific induction
34 347 conditions for 7 days, and the expression of the osteogenic (*RUNX2*, *COL1A1*, *ALPL*, and
35 348 *OCN*) or adipogenic (*CEBPA*, *PPARG*) genes was assessed by qPCR analysis (Fig. 3).
36 349

37 The significantly lower expression of early osteogenic genes (*RUNX2*, *ALPL*, and
38 350 *OCN*) was detected in primed MSCs compared to their unprimed counterparts. The most
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352 remarkable differences were observed in the expression of *RUNX2* (around 20-fold), and
353 ALPL expression was nearly abrogated. The expression of *COL1A1* was low, independent of
354 the priming conditions (Fig. 3). No differences in the morphology between the primed and
355 unprimed cells were detected after osteogenic induction. Only a few cells in both groups were
356 positive for alkaline phosphatase staining (Additional file 3, Fig. 1S).

357 A similar cytokine licensing effect was detected during the adipogenic induction. The
358 expression of *CEBPA* and *PPARG* genes was significantly downregulated after the short-term
359 TNF- α and IFN- γ exposure. Similar morphological changes were detected after adipogenic
360 induction of primed and unprimed WJ-MSCs, which were accompanied by the initiation of lipid
361 droplet formation, confirmed by Nile red staining (Additional file 3, Fig. 1S). The quantitative
362 analysis of Nile red fluorescence revealed a higher accumulation of lipid droplets in unprimed
363 cultures.

364 These results demonstrate the inhibitory effect of the priming on the early stages of
365 adipogenic and osteogenic differentiation of WJ-MSCs.

366 ***Effect of cytokine licensing on the growth factor secretion***

367 The paracrine activity of the MSCs is considered a primary driver of their therapeutic
368 potential. To investigate potential alterations in growth factor production induced by cytokine
369 treatment, the concentrations of six proteins (EGF, FGF-2, HGF, LIF, SCF, VEGF-A, and
370 VEGF-C) were measured in the conditioned medium. Such growth factor panel reflects the
371 non-immune-related therapeutic capacity of WJ-MSCs, representing their angiogenic and
372 cytoprotective potential (Fig. 4A).

373 While the quantities of all growth factors were above the sensitivity threshold, the
374 maximal content in the range of 80-100 pg/ml was identified for HGF and LIF (Fig. 4A). The
375 cytokine licensing did not affect the production of EGF, FGF-2, HGF, LIF, and SCF. The only
376 significant increase ($p < 0.05$) was detected for VEGF-A and VEGF-C contents in the WJ-MSCs
377 conditioned medium following the short-term TNF- α and IFN- γ exposure.

378 To confirm that cytokine licensing promotes the immune-related paracrine capacity of
379 WJ-MSCs, we assessed the content of IL-8, CXCL10, CCL5, MCP1, IL-6, and sVCAM-1 in

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2 380 cell-derived secretome (Fig. 4B). As a result, a significant increase in the production of all
3 381 evaluated cytokines was detected, confirming the stimulatory effect of priming.

4 382 The results indicate a negligible immediate effect of cytokine priming on the production
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6 383 of non-immunomodulatory growth factors by WJ-MSCs.

7 8 9 384 ***Effect of cytokine licensing on cell metabolism***

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11 385 Considering the transcriptomics data (Fig. 1B), which showed mild alteration of
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13 386 pathways associated with OXPHOS and glycolysis, we focused on the metabolic state of the
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15 387 cells. The suppressed response of MSCs to the differentiation inducers following priming and
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17 388 the negligible effect on growth factor production may suggest a potentially silenced energy
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19 389 phenotype. In this context, we analysed log₂ fold change (log₂ FC) of gene sets linked to
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21 390 energy production – glycolysis and oxidative phosphorylation. Gene expression changes for
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23 391 both oxidative phosphorylation and glycolysis were relatively small between the two conditions
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25 392 (Additional file 3, Fig. 2S). The distribution of log₂ FC values revealed heterogeneity, with
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27 393 some genes being upregulated and some genes being downregulated. This heterogeneity
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29 394 suggests a possible alteration in oxygen consumption and ATP production. It is important to
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31 395 note that gene expression changes do not necessarily translate to functional metabolic activity.
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33 396 Therefore, in the next step, we analysed the metabolic activity of WJ-MSCs using the
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35 397 Seahorse metabolic flux analysis (Fig. 5).

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38 398 The metabolic analysis of WJ-MSCs confirmed alterations following cytokine priming.
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40 399 Surprisingly, the oxygen consumption rate (OCR) demonstrated a significant increase in both
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42 400 basal and maximal levels, indicating enhanced mitochondrial activity. Concurrently,
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44 401 extracellular acidification rate (ECAR) analysis showed an elevation in basal levels,
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46 402 suggesting an upregulation in glycolytic activity. However, no significant changes were
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48 403 observed in maximal ECAR levels.

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51 404 These findings suggest that cytokine priming may modulate the metabolic phenotype
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53 405 of WJ-MSCs, enhancing oxidative phosphorylation and basal glycolytic flux. Here, the TNF- α
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55 406 and IFN- γ treatment may induce an acute pro-inflammatory metabolic state, temporarily
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57 407 boosting glycolysis and mitochondrial activity to meet cellular energy demands for immune
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2 408 functions at the expense of other therapeutic capacities of MSCs, such as growth factor
3 409 secretion and differentiation.

4 410 To further assess the metabolic reprogramming of WJ-MSCs in response to cytokine
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6 411 licensing, we performed a global metabolomic analysis (Fig. 6). Similar to the gene expression
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8 412 analysis, the PCA showed a clear separation between primed and unprimed cell clusters,
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10 413 indicating substantial differences in metabolite profiles (Fig. 6A).

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13 414 The volcano plot highlights significant changes in multiple metabolite classes in
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15 415 cytokine-primed versus unprimed WJ-MSCs (Fig. 6B). TNF- α and IFN- γ licensing resulted in
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17 416 the reduction of the free amino acid (AA) levels with simultaneous increase of the cholesterol-
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19 417 esters (CE) and free fatty acids (FAs). A significant decrease in the phosphatidylcholines
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21 418 (PCs) levels along with an increase in lysophosphatidylcholines (LPCs) and
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23 419 lysophosphatidylethanolamines (LPE) were observed in cells after cytokine treatment (Fig.
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25 420 6C).

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28 421 Finally, the dot plot (Fig. 6D) illustrates the fold changes of individual metabolites. More
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30 422 specifically, the most prominent changes were associated with tryptophan breakdown via the
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32 423 kynurenine pathway (Fig. 6D). The remarkable increase in the content of kynurenine,
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34 424 accompanied by the dramatic decrease in the tryptophan level, was the major event that
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36 425 occurred in WJ-MSCs after the cytokine exposure. In addition, the polyamine N1 -
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38 426 acetylspermidine level was significantly increased in primed WJ-MSCs. We observed a higher
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40 427 content of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), namely FA 24:4 and FA 26:6, following the
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42 428 cytokine treatment (Fig. 6D). The significant upregulation of these metabolites points to
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44 429 enhanced amino acid catabolism and lipid turnover in primed samples.

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47 430 Obtained results collectively demonstrate that inflammatory activation of WJ-MSCs by
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49 431 cytokine licensing is an integrated response, which co-occurs with early metabolic and
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51 432 differentiation changes affecting cell therapeutic potential.

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55 434 **Discussion**

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435 In this study, we evaluated the effect of short-term priming of WJ-MSCs with pro-
436 inflammatory cytokines on the cell transcriptomic and metabolomic profiles, growth factor
437 secretion, and differentiation capacity. Consistent with the results of many research groups,
438 TNF- α and IFN- γ induced robust change in the transcriptomic landscape of cells with a
439 substantial shift towards anti-inflammatory immunomodulation (9-11). Here, we decided to
440 focus on the effect of cytokine treatment on key functional MSC characteristics, such as
441 differentiation capacity and growth factor secretion, that are not directly involved in
442 immunomodulation. The findings in this area remain limited, often controversial, and context-
443 dependent.

444 In our study, we found that cytokine licensing significantly reshapes the transcriptomic
445 and metabolomic profile of WJ-MSCs while suppressing their differentiation potential and
446 having minimal impact on their paracrine regenerative capacity.

447 At the transcriptomic level, the impact of TNF- α and IFN- γ exposure on cell
448 differentiation was unclear. We observed a nearly equal distribution of upregulated and
449 downregulated genes associated with differentiation in primed cells. [Heatmaps providing more](#)
450 [detailed information on osteogenic and adipogenic gene set changes are available in the](#)
451 [Additional materials \(Additional file 3, Fig. 5S and 6S, respectively\)](#). Considering the short
452 cytokine treatment duration (24 hours), we presumed that any effects would be more
453 noticeable during the initial stages of osteogenic and adipogenic induction, i.e. before the cells
454 readapt to the cytokine-free culture conditions.

455 Notably, early osteogenic markers (*RUNX2*, *ALPL*) were significantly downregulated
456 in cytokine-primed WJ-MSCs, while later markers (*COL1A1*, *OCN*) showed no change. Similar
457 observations have been reported in gingival MSCs after combined exposure to TNF- α
458 (10 ng/ml), IFN- γ (100 ng/ml), and IL-1b (1 ng/ml) (27). Interestingly, only a few publications
459 demonstrate the effect of dual TNF- α /IFN- γ treatment on the differentiation capacity of MSCs,
460 while available data for individual cytokines is controversial. For instance, IFN- γ has shown
461 both inhibitory and stimulatory effects on osteogenesis depending on the culture conditions
462 (28, 29). Similarly, the promotion of osteogenic differentiation by TNF- α (0.1 – 10 ng/ml) has

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2 463 been reported in (30, 31), while other studies reported that similar or higher concentrations
3 464 (10-100 ng/ml) had inhibitory action (32, 33).

4 465 It is important to note that osteogenesis is usually studied after a prolonged culture of
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6 466 cells in the differentiation medium, containing pro-inflammatory cytokines and osteogenic
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8 467 inducers, thus reflecting the overall effect of chronic inflammation. However, there is limited
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11 468 information concerning short-term cytokine exposure used for therapeutic MSC licensing.

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13 469 We can speculate that the observed suppression of osteogenesis in primed cells in our
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15 470 study correlated with the downregulation of the Wnt/ β -catenin signalling pathway, as
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17 471 evidenced by reduced expression of *WNT2*, *LRP4*, and *LGR4* (Fig. 3S in the Additional file 3).
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20 472 The Wnt/ β -catenin signalling is crucial for osteogenic differentiation of MSC (34, 35). When
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22 473 activated, the β -catenin accumulates in the cytoplasm and translocates to the nuclei,
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24 474 regulating the target osteogenic gene expression. Wnt signalling, in turn, can be affected by
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26 475 the TNF- α -induced activation of NF- κ B (36-38). It was shown that the TNF- α priming induced
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28 476 the β -catenin degradation in human MSCs via the activation of NF- κ B, leading to inhibition of
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31 477 the osteogenic differentiation of cells (37). This is in line with another clinical report showing
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33 478 that the enhanced NF- κ B signalling in systemic lupus erythematosus patients affected the
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35 479 Smad pathway in MSCs, which resulted in impaired osteogenesis (36). Moreover, the
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38 480 blockage of NF- κ B signalling pathway reversed the inhibitory effect of TNF- α , confirming the
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40 481 major role of this pathway in the osteogenesis (38). In addition to TNF- α , IFN- γ by activation
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42 482 of JAK-STAT transcriptional factors, can interfere with β -catenin complexes, reducing their
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44 483 translational activity and, thus, inhibiting the Wnt signalling (39).

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47 484 Indeed, the short-term exposure of WJ-MSCs to TNF- α /IFN- γ in our study led to the
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49 485 upregulation of *NFKB1*, *STAT1*, *JAK2*, and *JAK3* based on RNA-seq data (Fig. 3S in the
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51 486 Additional file 3).

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53 487 In parallel, JAK-STAT activation drove significant upregulation of IDO1, which
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55 488 catalysed tryptophan catabolism and resulted in the accumulation of end product - kynurenine,
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58 489 as confirmed by our metabolomics analysis (Fig. 5D, Fig. 3S in the Additional file 3). Similarly,
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60 490 in the study evaluating the effect of IFN- γ on human and mouse MSCs, accumulation of

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2 491 kynurenine and simultaneous tryptophan depletion was observed, which led to the inhibition
3 of osteogenesis (40).

4 493 Kynurenine has been shown to modulate downstream transcriptional activity of Aryl
5 hydrocarbon receptor (AhR), suppressing MSC osteogenic differentiation (41). Since IDO-
6 494 mediated tryptophan catabolism represented the major change in the overall metabolomics
7 landscape of primed WJ-MSCs, we presumed that it might be the primary mechanism
8 495 contributing to impaired cell differentiation potential. To confirm this idea, we tried to rescue
9 differentiation using 1-methyl tryptophan (1-MT), an IDO inhibitor. Surprisingly, in our study,
10 no differences were noticed in the expression of differentiation markers compared to 1-MT-
11 496 free group following 7 days of osteogenic or adipogenic induction (Fig. 4S in the Additional file
12 3). This lack of effect is likely due to 1-MT's paradoxical role as an activator of AhR,
13 independent of its IDO inhibition (42, 43). Therefore, we may presume that the strategy of IDO
14 497 blockade by synthetic inhibitors, such as 1-MT, may not be efficient enough for improving the
15 differentiation capacity of MSCs impaired by the pro-inflammatory cytokines.
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31 505 Interestingly, adipogenic differentiation was also inhibited following cytokine priming
32 despite the downregulation of Wnt signalling and activation of AhR, both of which can promote
33 506 adipogenesis (44, 45). The opposite effect demonstrated in our study (i.e., decreased PPAR γ
34 expression) may be attributable to the dominance of other pathways activated by multifaceted
35 507 effects of IFN- γ and TNF- α . It has been recently shown that cytokine licensing inhibits the
36 adipocyte differentiation of MSCs by affecting the peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor
37 gamma coactivator 1-alpha (PGC-1 α), a master regulator of cellular antioxidant defence (46).
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46 512 Indeed, our findings are consistent with the hypothesis that cytokine priming causes
47 mild oxidative stress. As a counterweight to it, the upregulation of protective mechanisms is
48 513 initiated, leading to an increase of the superoxide dismutase 2 (SOD2) gene expression (Fig.
49 514 3S in the Additional file 3). SOD2, in turn, can scavenge the mitochondrial reactive oxygen
50 species, which promotes the adipogenic differentiation of MSCs (46, 47). Therefore, the short-
51 515 term cytokine treatment initiates the complex cascade of events, suppressing both osteogenic
52 and adipogenic differentiation of WJ-MSCs.
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2 520 Therefore, considering our data and published studies of other research groups, we
3 may presume that the WJ-MSC licensing by the mixture of IFN- γ and TNF- α drives the
4 521 complex cascade of molecular events, affecting cells' differentiation capacity.
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6 522 We have further analysed the cytokine priming's impact on selected growth factor
7 secretion and found minimal effects. In our study, only VEGF-A release was significantly
8 523 increased but remained at low levels specific to this MSC tissue source (1). These findings
9 align with results shown after IFN- γ treatment of iPSC-derived MSCs during 5 days in culture
10 524 (48). In another study (49), authors demonstrated an increase in the content of VEGF-A and
11 FGF-2 following priming of umbilical cord MSCs with TNF- α (250 U/ml, 48 hours). Elevated
12 525 levels of VEGF-A were detected following priming of bone marrow MSCs with TNF- α (20
13 ng/ml) and IFN- γ (20 ng/ml) for 24 hours (50). Our analysis showed that in contrast to VEGF-
14 526 A, the FGF-2 protein level remained unchanged, yet the expression of the *FGF2* gene was
15 significantly upregulated, suggesting post-transcriptional regulation (Fig. 3S in the Additional
16 527 file 3).
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31 533 It is worth noting that VEGF-C, rather than VEGF-A, has been proposed as a key factor
32 in enhancing wound healing following IFN- γ /TNF- α priming of umbilical cord MSCs (51).
33 534 Referring to the transcriptomic analysis conducted in our study, we confirmed that the *VEGFC*
34 gene expression was noticeably increased (Fig. 3S in the Additional file 3). Moreover, the
35 535 enhanced content of the VEGF-C protein was detected in the conditioned medium of cytokine-
36 licensed cells, compared to their unprimed counterparts (Fig. 4A).
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45 539 Previously, we demonstrated that HGF production, compared to other growth factors,
46 is dominant in WJ-MSCs (1). In the current study, while HGF levels remained higher than
47 540 VEGF-A, no significant changes were detected following TNF- α /IFN- γ exposure. Moreover,
48 HGF gene expression was significantly downregulated (Fig. 3S in the Additional file 3),
49 541 consistent with findings of the study focusing on cytokine-licensed endometrial MSCs (15
50 ng/ml TNF- α and 10 ng/ml IFN- γ for 48 hours), where the authors reported passage-
51 542 dependent *HGF* expression decrease (52). The reduction of HGF production was detected
52 after 72 hrs of priming of umbilical cord MSCs by 10 ng/mL IFN- γ and 15 ng/mL TNF- α (53).
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2 548 Discrepancies in reported data concerning growth factor secretion may arise from
3 variations in licensing methods (cytokine concentration and treatment duration) and the tissue
4 549 source of MSCs.

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6 550 Given the growing evidence that the secretory activity of MSCs is closely linked to their
7 metabolic state, in the next step, we evaluated the metabolic profile of the cells by studying
8 551 the mitochondrial respiration, glycolytic rate, and the changes in the metabolomics landscape.
9 the mitochondrial respiration, glycolytic rate, and the changes in the metabolomics landscape.
10 552 We confirmed that cytokine priming resulted in remarkable alterations of the WJ-MSCs
11 metabolomics profile. Predictably, the most pronounced effect corresponded to IDO-mediated
12 553 tryptophan breakdown via the kynurenine pathway, which is considered one of the main
13 554 drivers of the immunomodulatory activity of MSCs (54).
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22 557 Among the other metabolites with known effects on stem cell fate, we identified an
23 increased level of polyamine N1-acetylspermidine in primed WJ-MSCs. This polyamine has
24 558 been shown to positively influence stemness characteristics of hair follicle stromal cells (55).
25 559 Furthermore, the reduction in phosphatidylcholines (PC) content observed in our study can be
26 560 associated with the decrease in the senescence levels (56). We also found an increased
27 561 content of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) after cytokine licensing. PUFAs, beyond their
28 562 notable effect on immune cells, have been shown to positively affect MSC differentiation (57).
29 563 It has also been reported that unsaturated FAs have a beneficial effect on the secretome
30 564 profile of MSCs (58).
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42 566 In addition, following the cytokine treatment, we observed increased cholesterol-esters
43 (CE) levels. It is known that the cholesterol content affects the adhesion properties of MSCs
44 567 and differentiation. For instance, the accumulation of the CE in mouse MSCs improved their
45 568 osteogenic commitment (59, 60). On the one hand, the increased synthesis of the PUFAs,
46 569 CE, or N1-acetylspermidine may contribute to enhanced differentiation capacity of the cells or
47 570 the secretion of growth factors. On the other hand, IDO-mediated tryptophan breakdown,
48 571 accompanied by the remarkable accumulation of kynurenine, may lead to the inhibition of
49 572 differentiation in MSCs.
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574 While our data offer an overview of transcriptomic, metabolic, and functional changes
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2 575 of WJ-MSCs in response to the TNF- α / IFN- γ licensing, the presumed above molecular
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4 576 mechanisms necessitate additional in-depth validation at the protein level. Furthermore,
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6 577 considering the overall complexity of the events initiated by the cytokine treatment, uncovering
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8 578 the precise molecular mechanisms requires the analysis of the effect of IFN- γ and TNF- α
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10 579 separately with further comparison of their combinatorial action. Despite these limitations, we
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12 580 believe that the provided analysis may represent significant value for translational stem cell
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14 581 research and may be used to further improve the therapeutic performance of the MSCs.
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17 582 **Conclusions**

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20 583 These results highlight the complex and multifaceted influence of the dual treatment of
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22 584 WJ-MSCs by combining IFN- γ and TNF- α . The cytokine priming simultaneously affects
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24 585 various signalling and metabolic pathways, which interact and compete with each other,
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26 586 resulting in a unique synchronized cellular phenotype. We revealed that the priming effect is
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28 587 dual in nature: while it enhances the immunomodulatory phenotype, it simultaneously impairs
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30 588 such crucial MSC function as differentiation. Here, we challenge the universality of cytokine
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32 589 priming as a pre-treatment strategy for diverse MSC-based therapeutic applications and
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34 590 emphasize the importance of further studies of complex crosstalk between pathways activated
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36 591 in response to priming. A comprehensive analysis of the interplay between changes in cellular
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38 592 processes - including gene expression, secretome release, metabolomic landscape, and
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40 593 bioenergetic activity - will allow finding the optimal licensing strategy required for specific
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42 594 clinical applications and ensure reproducible and effective outcomes.
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596 **List of abbreviations**

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597 1-MT - 1-Methyl tryptophan

598 AA - amino acid

599 AhR - aryl hydrocarbon receptor

600 ALP - alkaline phosphatase

601 [CCL5 - chemokine ligand 5](#)

602 CE - cholesterol-esters

603 CEBPA - CCAAT/enhancer-binding protein alpha

604 COL1A1 - collagen type I alpha 1 chain

605 [CXCL10 - C-X-C motif chemokine ligand 10](#)

606 ECAR - extracellular acidification rate

607 EGF - epidermal growth factor

608 FA - fatty acids

609 FGF - fibroblast growth factor

610 GSEA - gene set enrichment analysis

611 GO - gene ontology

612 HGF - hepatocyte growth factor

613 HLA-G - human leukocyte antigen-g

614 IDO - indoleamine 2,3-dioxygenase

615 IFN- γ - interferon-gamma

616 [IL – interleukin](#)

617 JAK-STAT - Janus kinase/signal transducer and activator of transcription

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3 618 KEGG - Kyoto encyclopedia of genes and genomes
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5 619 LIF - leukemia inhibitory factor
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7 620 LPCs - lysophosphatidylcholines
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9 621 LPEs - lysophosphatidylethanolamines
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11 622 [LC-MS - liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry](#)
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13 623 [MCP-1 - monocyte chemoattractant protein-1](#)
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15 624 MSC – multipotent mesenchymal stromal cell
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17 625 NF-kB/NFKB - nuclear factor kappa b
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19 626 OCN - osteocalcin
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21 627 OCR - oxygen consumption rate
22
23 628 OXPHOS - oxidative phosphorylation
24
25 629 PCs - phosphatidylcholines
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27 630 PD-L1 - programmed death-ligand 1
28
29 631 PGE2 - prostaglandin e2
30
31 632 PGC-1 α - proliferator-activated receptor gamma coactivator 1-alpha
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33 633 PPARG - peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma
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35 634 PUFAs - polyunsaturated fatty acids
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37 635 RUNX2 - runt-related transcription factor 2
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39 636 SCF - stem cell factor
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41 637 SOD2 - superoxide dismutase 2
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43 638 [sVCAM-1 – soluble vascular cell adhesion protein 1](#)
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45 639 TNF- α - tumor necrosis factor-alpha
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640 VEGF - vascular endothelial growth factor

641 WJ-MSC - Wharton's jelly multipotent mesenchymal stromal cell

642

643 **Declarations**

644 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

645 All experimental procedures were conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki,
646 as well as relevant ethical guidelines and regulations.

647 The study on was approved under the project "Safety and efficacy evaluation of allogeneic
648 mesenchymal stem cells derived from umbilical cord tissue in repair of cartilage defects:
649 preclinical study on animal model" by the Ethics Committee of the Institute of Experimental
650 Medicine of the Czech Academy of Sciences, No. 2017/07 on 9.07.2017. The informed
651 consent for umbilical cord tissue collection was obtained from all subjects and/or their legal
652 guardian(s).

653 **Consent for publication**

654 Not applicable.

655 **Availability of data and materials**

656 The data supporting this study's findings are openly available on Zenodo under the title Data
657 supporting the article "The role of cytokine licensing in shaping the therapeutic potential of
658 Wharton's jelly MSCs: a metabolic shift towards immunomodulation at the expense of
659 differentiation." The repository includes all figures, raw and processed transcriptomic and
660 metabolomics data, and a list of GO terms used in this research. The dataset can be accessed
661 at <https://zenodo.org/records/14635601>

662 **Competing interests**

663 All authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this study.

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673 **Authors' contributions**

674 OR, KS, YP – concept and design of the study, data analysis and interpretation, manuscript
675 writing, OR, EV, IV, KG, JH, KS, YP - experiments execution, collection and assembly of data;
676 MS, PR – preparation of libraries and contribution to the RNA-seq analysis, PA and KS –
677 bioinformatics, SK, LB, PJ - critical review of the manuscript, administrative and financial
678 support; KS, YP - supervision of the study. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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683 [Academy of Sciences for metabolomics and lipidomics analysis.](#) The authors declare that they
684 have not used AI-generated work in this manuscript.

685 **Author information**

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19 863 **Figure legends**

22 864 Figure 1. Changes in the transcriptomic profile of WJ-MSCs (N=7) following the cytokine
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24 865 licensing:

27 866 A – Principal component analysis (PCA) of transcriptome data from unprimed (light blue) and
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29 867 primed (dark blue) samples.

32 868 B – Volcano plot depicting pathway-level enrichment analysis across the Human collections
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34 869 of Molecular Signatures Database (Hallmark gene sets, WikiPathways gene sets, KEGG
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36 870 Medicus gene sets, Reactome gene sets, and GO biological process gene sets) representing
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38 871 the overview of the major pathways responded to the cytokine priming. Each point represents
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40 872 a distinct pathway, with the x-axis showing the normalized enrichment scores (NES) and the
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42 873 y-axis displaying the $-\log_{10}$ adjusted p-value. The colour coding corresponds to the biological
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44 874 database.

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49 875 C – Enrichment plots for two hallmark gene sets significantly upregulated in primed samples:
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51 876 Interferon Gamma Response and TNFA signalling via NFKB pathways. Green curves
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53 877 represent the enrichment score (ES), while black bars indicate the position of genes within the
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55 878 ranked list.

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880 Figure 2. Distribution of up- and downregulated genes (log 2 fold changes, FC) referred to cell
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2 881 differentiation following cytokine priming based on analysis of the Gene ontology (GO) terms.
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4 882 The following GO terms are presented: GO:0002062 Chondrocyte differentiation,
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6 883 GO:0045445 Myoblast differentiation, GO:0035914 Skeletal muscle cell differentiation,
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8 884 GO:0051145 Smooth muscle cell differentiation, GO:0045444 Fat cell differentiation,
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11 885 GO:0001649 Osteoblast differentiation, GO:0030182 Neuron differentiation, GO:0030154 Cell
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13 886 differentiation. The identified genes were then manually categorized based on fold change
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15 887 ranges (>1, 0.5–1, <0.5, <-0.5, -0.5 to -1, and >-1), and the number of genes in each category
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17 888 was used for the representation.
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23 890 Figure 3. The expression of osteogenic and adipogenic genes of unprimed and cytokine
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25 891 licensed WJ-MSCs (N=4, in duplicates) following the 7 days of the differentiation induction.
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28 892 Data is presented as Mean \pm SD relative expression of induced cells to control cells (not
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30 893 subjected to differentiation induction). Note: Ns – non-significant; * - p<0.05; ** - p<0.01.
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36 895 Figure 4. The content of secreted growth factors (A) and cytokines (B) in the conditioned
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38 896 medium of WJ-MSCs (N=4, in duplicates). Data is presented as Mean \pm SD. Note: * - p<0.05.
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41 897
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44 898 Figure 5. The oxygen consumption rate (OCR) (A, B) and extracellular acidification rate
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46 899 (ECAR) (D, E) of the unprimed and cytokine licensed WJ-MSCs (N=6, in triplicates) assessed
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48 900 using Seahorse assay. Representative traces of OCR (C) and ECAR (F) were obtained and
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51 901 shown for primed and unprimed (control) cells. Note: Ns – non-significant; * - p<0.05; ** -
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53 902 p<0.01; *** - p<0.001.
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2 904 Figure 6. Metabolomic and lipidomic profile of WJ-MSCs following the cytokine licensing (N=4,
3 905 in duplicates):
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5 906 A - Principal component analysis (PCA) of metabolomic data from unprimed (light blue) and
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7 907 primed (dark blue) WJ-MSCs samples.
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10 908 B – Volcano plot depicting the clear separation of the main metabolite classes in WJ-MSCs
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12 909 induced by the cytokine priming. Each point represents a distinct most enriched metabolite
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14 910 within the pathway, [while its colour denotes the specific metabolite class it belongs to.](#)
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16
17 911 Abbreviations: Tricarboxylic acid cycle metabolites (TCA), triglycerides (TG), free fatty acids
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19 912 (FAs), lysophosphatidylcholines (LPC), lysophosphatidylethanolamines (LPE), cholesterol
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21 913 esters (CE), and amino acids (AAs).
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24 914 C – The changes in selected metabolite families in WJ-MSCs following the cytokine priming
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26 915 Note: Ns – non-significant; * - $p < 0.05$; ** - $p < 0.01$.
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28
29 916 D – Dot plot depicting \log_2 fold changes in metabolite levels between cytokine-primed WJ-
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31 917 MSCs and unprimed controls. Each dot represents a metabolite, with its position indicating
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33 918 the magnitude of fold change (\log_2) and its color/size denoting statistical significance: [small](#)
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35 919 [black dot \(\$p < 0.05\$ \), medium grey dot \(\$p < 0.01\$ \), big white dot \(\$p < 0.001\$ \).](#)
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41 921 **Additional files**

42 922 **Additional file 1.pdf**

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48 923 Table 1. The list of the most up- or down-regulated genes (\log_2 fold > 1 , $p < 0.001$), detected in
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50 924 RNA-seq results
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52 53 925 [Additional file 2.pdf](#) 54 55 56 57 58 59 60 61 62 63 64 65

1
2 927 Table 1. The list of the genes related to MSC differentiation with log2 fold change in expression
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4 928 after cytokine priming, compared to unprimed cells, using a p-value threshold of 0.05, detected
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7 929 in RNA-seq results
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10 930 **Additional file 3.pdf**
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13 931 Figure 1S. Morphological properties and indicators of osteogenic (alkaline phosphatase
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15 932 staining) and adipogenic (Nile red staining) induction of unprimed (upper row) and primed
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17 933 (lower row) WJ-MSCs. The graph shows the quantitative analysis of adipogenic differentiation
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19 934 assessed by the intensity of Nile red staining, normalized to the number of cells (100,000
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21 935 cells).
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25 936 Figure 2S. The volcano plot comparing gene sets related to HALLMARK_OXPHOS (oxidative
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27 937 phosphorylation) and HALLMARK_GLYCOLYSIS (glycolysis) in primed and unprimed WJ-
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29 938 MSCs. The x-axis represents the log2 fold change (FC), while the y-axis shows the -log10 p-
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31 939 adjusted values. Each dot indicates a differentially expressed gene after priming.
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34 940 Figure 3S. Changes in the expression of genes of interest after short-term cytokine licensing.
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37 941 Figure 4S. The expression of osteogenic and adipogenic genes of unprimed and cytokine-
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39 942 licensed WJ-MSCs (N=4 in duplicates) with and without IDO inhibition.
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42 943 Figure 5S. Heatmap of changes occurred in the expression of genes related to osteogenic
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44 944 differentiation. The genes with a log2 fold change in expression after cytokine priming,
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46 945 compared to unprimed cells, were identified according to GO:0001649 (osteoblast
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48 946 differentiation), using a p-value threshold of 0.05.
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51
52 947 Figure 6S. Heatmap of changes occurred in the expression of genes related to adipogenic
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54 948 differentiation. The genes with a log2 fold change in expression after cytokine priming,
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56 949 compared to unprimed cells, were identified according to GO:0045444 (fat cell differentiation),
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58 950 using a p-value threshold of 0.05.
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